

A Quantitative Evaluation of the Prediction Performance of a One-Dimensional Multifluid Population Balance Model in Continuous and Semi-Batch Bubble Columns

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to evaluate the efficacy of a one-dimensional multifluid population balance model (1D-MPB) in predicting the axial variation of the bubble size distribution (BSD), gas phase velocity, and gas volume fraction in a bubble column. The bubble column was operated in either a semi-batch mode, without liquid feed, or a continuous mode, with co-current liquid and gas feed. The model's predictions were compared with experimental data obtained through minimal invasive fiber optic needle probes. The experiments were carried out with different spargers and varying gas and liquid fluxes. The model parameters were previously determined in a different study. The findings indicate that the model accurately predicts the BSD, Sauter mean diameter and local gas volume fractions, particularly at medium gas fluxes in semi-batch mode. The application of a modified sparger model to predict inlet BSDs demonstrated potential, although limitations were observed at higher fluxes. In continuous co-current mode, the model (parameterized with data from semi-batch experiments), exhibited robust prediction performance without the need for recalibration, indicating the soundness of the underlying physical principles and the value of the method for scale-up. Future work will focus on refining the turbulent energy dissipation model to enhance the model's accuracy and applicability for industrial bubble column design and optimization.

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1. Introduction

Bubble columns (BCs) are standard multiphase reactors utilized in processes such as fermentation, gas adsorption, for stripping or gas liquid reactions such as oxidation, hydrogenation and hydroformylations [1, 2]. To scale-up these processes from laboratory to production and design the appropriate reactor vessels, engineers need insights into the influence of process conditions, system properties, and reactor geometry on the behavior of the multiphase process, including the conversion of reactants and selectivity to target products. Experimental methods often fall short in providing these insights due to the numerous parameter combinations and the scale differences between laboratory and production. Thus, models are required that can describe these interactions reliably in a large parameter range.

Three-dimensional computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is a potential tool for model-based design and optimization, theoretically capable of mapping all interactions. However, its high resource demands make comprehensive studies of process and design parameters impractical [3, 4]. Engineers often require general trends concerning the interaction of system properties, process conditions, and reactor geometry to identify unfavorable operating windows or reactor designs and to interpret observations from real production processes.

A promising alternative is our one-dimensional multifluid population balance model (1D-MPB), which offers a fast and reliable method to map these interactions [5–7]. It is based on the kinetic gas theory approach with size resolution (KTAWSR), developed by Jakobsen and colleagues [8–10]. The 1D-MPB approach employs the assumption frequently utilized to describe the behaviors of columns, whereby the physical space is simplified to a single dimension along the main flow direction. The complex behavior of dispersed phase, such as breakage, coalescence, nucleation, and growth, as well as the size-dependent velocity of bubbles, is described by the KTAWSR. Jakobsen and colleagues [8–10] derived new transport equations (mass, species mass, energy, momentum) for the dispersed phase that, like the population balance equation (PBE), depend on the property space (e.g., bubble size). Using the KTAWSR approach, in addition to the PBE, we account for the transport of momentum in the gas phase, making bubble velocity a function of their size allowing a stronger coupling of the equations and more precise description of the residence time of the bubbles in the column. Consequently, the properties of the gas phase, including axial velocity, temperature, and composition, are not solely dependent on the axial position within the column; they become also functions of the bubble diameter. This methodology permits the description of the intricate interplay between temperature, composition, and the residence time of the phases, as well as mass transfer and reaction (as it was shown for a test case by Vik *et al.* [10]).

In a first study [5], we successfully applied the MPB approach to a miniplant bubble column (DN 100) without liquid feed (semi-batch mode). We calibrated different breakage and coalescence

kernels to measured bubble size distributions (BSD) along the bubble column height for different gas fluxes. That means the model parameter were estimated using a least-square-method. After parameter calibration, all kernels performed similarly well. In a second study [6], we used cross-validation to show that the amount of experimental data needed to calibrate the model can be significantly reduced. At present, only measurements of the BSD (or two of its moments) taken at a single axial position within the column for two different gas fluxes are necessary to estimate four model parameters (referred to as one-point calibration in the following text). The four model parameters are each represented in the birth and death terms of the breakage and coalescence kernels. The performance of this one-point calibrated model was rigorously evaluated through a comprehensive comparison between the model prediction and the actual measurements obtained under a variety of conditions, including different liquid levels (holdups), gas fluxes, axial measurement positions, and binary mixtures of water and four distinct solutes (ethanol, sodium chloride, sodium sulfite and glycerol) with varying concentration. The findings indicated that the model is capable of accurately predicting the BSD along the column height and the gas holdup in a satisfactory manner for a given aqueous solution (binary mixture) across a broad range of process conditions.

In order to demonstrate the applicability of our methodology for the scale-up of bubble columns, it is necessary to prove that the model is capable of predicting states that are situated even further outside the regime to which it was calibrated. Thus, a new series of experiments was conducted with the objective of determining the influence of the different designs of gas spargers on the properties of the dispersed gas phase in the column operated in semi-batch mode. Furthermore, the operation mode was altered to a continuous co-current mode with feed of gas and liquid phase. The experimental data was subjected to a comparison with the model predictions. Nevertheless, the model was not recalibrated; rather, the four model parameters from our previous work [6] (estimated with experimental data obtained in the semi-batch model), were utilized.

Further in the previous studies [5, 6], an optical image measurement technique, the optical multimode online probe (OMOP) [11], was used in order to measure the BSDs. A key issue in the use of OMOP is the extent to which it affects the measured BSD, given its invasive nature. In this work instead, fiber optic needle probes (NP) based on Laser Doppler Anemometry [12] were used, which are significantly less invasive than the OMOP and are practically unrestricted in terms of gas volume fraction and gas velocity. The NP enables the recording of BSDs at higher gas fluxes, and it can also determine the local gas volume fraction. This feature allows for the comparison of predicted and measured local gas volume fractions. However, it is challenging to directly compare the size distributions determined with different measurement techniques, even when the invasiveness of the measurement technique on the flow and the BSD are disregarded. This is because both OMOP and NP measure different size distributions. The OMOP measures the size based on a two-dimensional shadowgraphic image of the bubbles [13], whereas the NP measures the distribution of the piercing length (for details please refer to Section 2 and Lefebvre *et al.* [12]). Consequently, the absolute values measured are not comparable in principle. This also applies to other measurement techniques, such as grating sensors or lasers [14]. In essence, however, our primary objective is not to ascertain the absolute BSDs, but rather to utilize the measured BSDs to estimate model parameters and to evaluate the prediction performance. It is hypothesized that the choice of measurement technique has no influence on the resulting model

parameters and predictions. The estimated model parameters exert an influence on the occurrence of breakage and coalescence, which in turn affects the manner in which the BSD and dispersed phase velocity change along the height of the column (shape and appearance). The position of the BSD (corresponding to the mean bubble diameter) is primarily influenced by the inlet distribution generated by the sparger. Consequently, provided that the different measurement techniques reflect the same trends of the BSD with respect to the parameter variations, the model parameters determined for the different measurement data should be similar. To assess the hypothesis, the model parameters, calibrated with the OMOP, are applied without recalibration to the BSD measured with the NP and the prediction performance is evaluated.

As previously stated, the inlet BSD produced by the gas sparger exerts a significant influence on the BSD along the column height. In order to solve our model equations, it is necessary to specify the inlet BSD as a mathematical boundary condition (for further details, please refer to Breit *et al.* [6] Supplementary Information). In our previous studies [5, 6], we utilised the BSD measured just above the gas sparger (about 20 cm) as the boundary condition. The application of a measured BSD as a boundary condition restricts the scope of our model approach. It is not feasible to employ this approach for scaling up of bubble columns, as in industrial-scale bubble columns, the inlet BSD is rarely, if ever, measured. A model is required that can reliably predict the BSD produced by the gas sparger as a function of the sparger geometry and the operating conditions. Consequently, in this study, a modified model approach, as proposed by Ribeiro *et al.* [15], was tested. The BSDs predicted by the sparger model were compared to the measured inlet BSDs.

In this work, we were able to successfully apply the MBP without recalibration to different spargers in semi-batch operation and for the first time to continuous co-current operation. Thereby, the experimental reference data was acquired using needle probes instead of an optical imaging method. The model was able to reproduce the measured data by the needle probe, but limitations were found at higher gas fluxes. The results demonstrate that the proposed one-dimensional multifluid population balance model is capable of adequately describing the local bubble size distribution and the local gas volume fraction in the BC for diverse operational conditions (without liquid feed, co-current feed of gas and liquid, and different gas spargers) with a single set of model parameters. Overall, the findings suggest that the presented MPB is a valuable tool for the scale-up of bubble columns.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Experimental Setup and Procedure

Fig. 2.1 depicts the experimental setup employed in this study. Two operating modes were possible: 1) continuous gas feed without continuous liquid feed (referred to as semi-batch mode), and 2) continuous co-current gas and liquid feed (referred to as continuous mode). The bubble column (2, the number refers to Fig. 2.1) consisted of three column sections. The longest column section in the bottom (5) was made of austenitic stainless steel up to a height of $h \approx 200$ cm with an internal diameter of $d_{BC} \approx 10.6$ cm. This column section was followed by a small transparent pipe section (6) made of polymethyl methacrylate ($(d, h) \approx (10, 30)$ cm). It is used as a viewing window. The upper column section (7) is a T-piece ($(d, h) \approx (11, 50)$ cm) made of unplasticized polyvinyl chloride. It serves as a side overflow ($d \approx 5$ cm).

Figure 2.1.: Schematic illustration of the experimental setup.

In both operating modes, compressed air from the utility supply was dispersed at the bottom ($z = 0$ cm) into the column through a plate sparger (4, PIS) in semi-batch mode or a spider sparger (3, SpS) in continuous mode. The air was purged to the ambient at the column top. Geometric details of the employed spargers including there abbreviations are summarized in the

Supplementary Information Tab. S.7. The gas flux j_d was regulated by a mass flow controller (1) from the manufacturer Brooks Instrument (Hateld, Pennsylvania, USA) of the GF040 series (GF040CXXC-0008030L-N2AVS5-XXXXXX-00C). In semi-batch mode the column was filled with osmosis water (conductivity about 0.01 mS cm^{-1} , in the following referred just as water) before starting the gas flow. The level of the ungasified liquid h_c was measured from the plate sparger. In continuous mode, the liquid (water) was fed into the column from the buffer tank (8) and it left the column via the side overflow ($z \approx 2.535 \text{ m}$) from where it flowed back into the buffer tank (8). The buffer tank also served the function of a gas-liquid separator. A centrifugal pump (9) of type MPN170PP from manufacturer SCHMITT Kreiselpumpen GmbH & Co. KG (Ettlingen, Germany) was used to convey the liquid. The liquid inlet was situated in a central position at the base of the column ($d \approx 3.44 \text{ cm}$, $z \approx -10.5 \text{ cm}$). The liquid volume flow rate, or the liquid flux j_c , was determined using a Coriolis mass flow meter (11) of type PROMASS 80 (80F15-10H0/0) from manufacturer Endress+Hauser (Reinach, Switzerland). The liquid flow rate was manually controlled using the frequency inverter (10) of type DC1 (DC1-349D5NB-A6SCE1) from the manufacturer EATON (Bonn, Germany) to adjust the rotational speed of the pump.

2.2. Measurement Techniques

To determine the BSD at the three axial positions (M1, M2, M3, see Tab. S.9 for details) along the height of the BC, fiber optic needle probes (5, NP) of type M2 from manufacturer A2 Photonic Sensors (Grenoble, France) were used. Fiber optic needle probes are based on laser Doppler anemometry [12, 16]. A comprehensive description of the measuring principle and application of NP can be found in [12, 16]. The following paragraph provides a concise overview based on these sources:

A laser beam generated by an optoelectronic module (OPTOEM) is sent via an optical fiber to the conical glass fiber tip of the probe. The laser is reflected from the surrounding phase back into the tip to the OPTOEM, whereby the intensity of the reflected signal depends on the refractive index of the surrounding phase. Since the refractive index of the dispersed and continuous phase is different, the surrounding phase can be determined. The OPTOEM converts the reflected light signal into a digital signal and uses this to determine the penetration time and the pierced phase. In addition, the velocity of the pierced bubble can be determined from the signal using the Doppler effect. With the information of the velocity and piercing time, the size of a individual bubble can be calculated. The validity of each measured bubble is evaluated using the detected signal based on the velocity measurement. A valid velocity measurement occurs whenever the tip of the probe pierces the surface of the bubble almost perpendicularly. In addition to the size and the velocity of the bubbles, the local gas volume fraction can be determined in a separate measurement using the NP. The ratio of sum of the piercing time to the total measurement time gives the local gas volume fraction.

The advantages and disadvantages of this measuring technique result from the design and the measuring principle. On one hand, it is minimally invasive (tip diameter 0.125 mm , for further dimensions see Fig. S.1) and the size and velocity of the bubbles as well as the local gas volume

fraction can be determined with a single measurement technique. The recorded data is considered to be accurate (5 % - 15 %) according to Lefebvre *et al.* [12]. The OMOP should also be in this order of magnitude of accuracy [5, 6]. On the other hand, only a 1D chord length measurement takes place. This disadvantage is further exacerbated by the validity check, which has the consequence that only bubbles that are pierced near their center, where the angle between tip and surface is close to 90° are incorporated. This has the overall consequence that we do not obtain a chord length distribution (CLD) in which all chords of the bubbles are recorded, for which at least semi-empirical conversion methods to a volume equivalent based BSD [17, 18] exist. The distributions recorded with the NP are somewhat akin to filtered CLD, or, according to the manufacturer, can be considered to be size distributions. Due to this filtering, the size distributions will be shifted towards smaller bubbles compared to the ground truth. Notwithstanding this difference, this size distribution is also referred to as BSD in the following.

In contrast, the OMOP [11] employed in our preceding studies [5, 6] records two-dimensional images from which the area and various diameters of the individual bubbles can be calculated, resulting in a BSD. However, this measurement technique presents several disadvantages, including invasiveness, a limitation of the maximum detectable bubble size due to optics and measurement gap size, and superposition of bubbles in the measurement gap that requires separation by computer-aided techniques (see, for example, [13]). In sum, these limitations restrict the application of the OMOP to lower phase fractions (approximately 20 %) for least non-spherical bubbles. Furthermore, due to shadow-graphic technology, e.g. umbrella bubbles are detected significantly larger in volume. Overall, it is estimated that the OMOP within its operating conditions measures larger bubble diameters compared to the ground truth.

Fig. S.2 in the Supplementary Information provides a comparison of the two measurement techniques measured BSD under the same operating conditions. However, the objective of this paper is not to provide a comprehensive comparison between NP and OMOP, nor to assess the precision of the associated measurement techniques. This is a topic that is left to other authors and future studies. The objective of this study is to assess the prediction performance of the 1D-MPB in greater detail. In this context, the NP is a valuable tool as it is less invasive than the OMOP, can measure at higher gas fluxes and gas volume fractions, and additionally measures the local gas volume fraction. Consequently, the potential of the NP as an alternative to the OMOP is being investigated in this paper. Moreover, the ground truth of the bubble size is of lesser importance, given that the objective is to identify trends and order of magnitude detection.

The OPTOEM and software settings used and further details about the NP are in the Supplementary Information S.4. A bubble size measurement contained at least 3000 valid bubbles and a local volume gas fraction measurement was performed for 30 s. The measured BSD and the measurement data for determining the gas volume fraction are provided in the Supplementary Material.

2.3. Overview of Experiments

An overview of the experiments is given in Tab. 2.1, the abbreviated sparger property's can be found in Tab. S.7 and the axial measuring position in Tab. S.9 in Supplementary Information. All experiments were carried out under ambient conditions ($T^0 \approx 293$ K, $p^0 \approx 1.0 \times 10^5$ Pa).

Table 2.1.: Summary of the experiments carried out.

Operation mode	$j_d / \text{cm s}^{-1}$	$j_c / \text{cm s}^{-1}$	Sparger	Measuring position
Semi-batch	1.0, 2.0,	0.0	PIS 04-187,	M1, M2,
	3.0, 4.0, 5.0			PIS 05-120
Continuous	1.0, 2.0,	1.0, 2.0, 3.0	SpS 04-56	M1, M2,
	3.0, 4.0			M3

3. Modelling and Simulation

3.1. Multifluid Population Balance Model

The model employed in this work is based on the assumption of steady-state conditions. All space-dependent quantities have been subjected to cross-sectional area averaging, resulting in the generation of a one-dimensional (1D) model aligned with the axial main flow direction (z). That is the plug-flow assumption. In the case of the continuous liquid phase (mass and momentum), the common multifluid model [19] is employed, while the KTAWSR [10] is utilized for the balance of momentum and mass of the gas phase. This allows for the velocity and mass of the dispersed phase (in this instance, bubbles) to be considered as a function of both the physical space (axial position, z) and the property space (bubble diameter, ξ). It should be noted that the size-dependent mass balance of the gas phase is represented by the PBE.

In this study, we employed the mass-based formulation of the PBE, as detailed in Breit *et al.* [20]. The solution of the equations of the MPB yields the mass density function, designated as f_d^m , and the velocity of the gas phase as functions of the axial position and bubble size. The mass density function enables the calculation of both the Sauter mean diameter (SMD) ξ_{32} (which represents a moment of the density function) and the local gas volume fraction α_d . The calculation formulas are summarized in the Supplementary Information S.1.

The model implementation and solution strategy are identical to those presented by Breit *et al.* [5], using the same simplification as suggest by Breit *et al.* [6]. Furthermore, the bubble growth due to axial pressure variations was neglected in this work. The growth of bubbles near the lower boundary of the property space leads to numerical artifacts mainly due to the denominator of the coalescence birth term. The denominator of the mass-based coalescence birth term contains the diameter and the volume of the bubble to be coalesced. Multiplying these two numbers, especially at the integration limits, produces extremely small numbers. If a number that is not sufficiently close to zero is divided by this extremely small number, values are created that are not physical (see detailed explanation and discussion [7, 20]). This problem did not occur in the previous studies [5, 6] because the lower boundary was at larger bubble diameters (compare 1×10^{-3} m to 5×10^{-5} m) where f_d^m was close to zero. Since the employed NPs enables detection of smaller bubbles than the OMOP (c.f. Section 2), the BSDs measured in this work are shifted to towards smaller bubbles (cf. Fig. S.2) compared to the BSDs measured in our previous studies [5, 6] so that f_d^m is non-zero at that small bubble sizes leading to the issue. In [7, 20], we discuss possible solutions, and in [7] we use a finite volume method instead of the spectral orthogonal collocation method used in this paper, which significantly reduces this problem. However, after a preliminary study it could be shown that in the cases considered here, growth has hardly any influence on the BSD compared to breakage and coalescence, so that the solution strategy and

its advantages over the finite volume method (cf. Breit *et al.* [7]) can be retained for the time being.

The turbulent energy dissipation rate was estimated using $\varepsilon = \sum_k j_k g$ according to [21, 22], where j_k is the flux of phase k and g the gravitational acceleration constant. This model is based on an energy balance about the reactor volume. For further detailed information on the model equations and solution strategy, please refer to the source publications [5, 6]. The parameters used in the simulations of this work are summarized in the Supplementary Information S.3.

3.2. Sparger Model

In this work, the inlet BSD (i.e. the boundary condition in the property space of the PBE) was taken from two different sources: 1) measurements of the BSD from just above the gas sparger as in our previous studies [5, 6], also referred to as measured inlet BSD below, 2) model predictions.

The model approach employed to describe the BSD at the gas sparger as a function of sparger geometry, property data of the fluids and process conditions (in the following referred to as sparger model) was adopted from Ribeiro *et al.* [15]. Ribeiro *et al.* [15] used the model according to Geary *et al.* [23] to determine the diameter of a single bubble formed at a single orifice. To obtain a distribution, Ribeiro *et al.* [15] fitted the two parameters (ω, χ) of a log-normal distribution to the measured BSD just above the sparger. Ribeiro *et al.* [15] considered one parameter of the log-normal distribution as the sparger parameter, the ω , and assumed it to be constant, although they could detect a dependence on the gas flux. The second parameter, the χ was re-fitted from Ribeiro *et al.* [15] to the bubble diameter formed at a single orifice resulting from the model of Geary *et al.* [23] in a second step. Therefore the model approach of Ribeiro *et al.* [15] allows the inter- and extrapolation to other gas fluxes and does not completely eliminate the need for experiments, it reduces the number of them.

We have modified the approach of Ribeiro *et al.* [15], because we have also found that ω is not constant, since it depends on the gas flux. In our case, however, to an extent that is no longer negligible. Furthermore, we found that the predicted bubble diameter according to Geary *et al.* [23] does not agree with our observations, which is why we additionally adjusted it using a further but constant parameter c for each sparger. Deviations of $\pm 20\%$ of the predicted bubble size according to Geary *et al.* [23] have already been observed by other researchers [24]. Furthermore, due to the available measurement connection ports in the bubble column, we were only able to record the first BSD approx. 20 cm above the sparger. At this distance, the bubbles have already experienced many breakage and coalescence events and the model according to Geary *et al.* [23] applies to a single orifice not to numerous neighboring ones, which may influence each other. However, using this additional parameter, good results could be achieved (cf. Section 4). Moreover, instead of using only Geary *et al.* [23] volume-equivalent bubble diameter for parameter estimation, as adapted by Ribeiro *et al.* [15], we included the SMD and standard deviation to fulfill additional moments of the distribution functions. The modified sparger model is briefly summarized in the Supplementary Information S.2.

3.3. Error Measure

Two different error measures are used to evaluate the prediction performance of our MPB. First, the mean absolute percentage error $MAPE$ of the moments of the distributions according to Eq. (3.1) is employed. Second, the symmetric Chi-Square distance χ^2 (see Eq. (3.2)) is used to evaluate the difference between predicted and measured BSD.

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N \frac{|\mu_{ab,i,\text{exp}} - \mu_{ab,i}|}{\mu_{ab,i,\text{exp}}} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\chi^2 = \sum_j \frac{\left(\hat{f}_d^n(\xi_j) - \hat{f}_{d,\text{exp}}^n(\xi_j)\right)^2}{\hat{f}_d^n(\xi_j) + \hat{f}_{d,\text{exp}}^n(\xi_j)} \quad (3.2)$$

Here $\mu_{ab,i}$ is the ab 'th moment ratio of a distribution function, ab is the order of the moment ratio (see Supplementary Information S.1), i is the index of incorporated moments and/or experiments, N is the number of incorporated moments and experiments, the subscript "exp" indicate a measured value, \hat{f}_d^n is the normalized number density function (see Eq. (S.4)), ξ is the bubble size and j is the index of the bubble size class. For a single statement about the χ^2 across several experiments, these are arithmetically averaged resulting in $\overline{\chi^2}$. The experiments to be averaged are marked in the superscript (M: for the measuring position, j_d, j_c for the gas resp. liquid fluxes), and the model is marked in the subscript (sim: simulation with measured inlet BSD, sim-SPM simulation with inlet BSD from sparger model, SPM: sparger model). In the case of the $MAPE$, the moment(s) with which it was formed is/are also identified in the subscript.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Semi-Batch Mode – Gas Flux and Sparger Study

Fig. 4.1 depicts both the measured and predicted Sauter mean diameter (SMD) ξ_{32} and the local gas volume fraction α_d as a function of the axial position z in the BC (semi-batch mode) for different gas fluxes j_d and for the two different spargers investigated. The simulation results were obtained using as boundary condition either the measured inlet BSD (sim) or the BSD predicted by the sparger model (sim-SPM).

Figure 4.1.: Top row (A)-(B): Sauter mean diameter ξ_{32} and bottom row (C)-(D): local gas volume fraction as function of the axial position z for different gas fluxes j_d (color) and spargers. Left column (A),(C): sparger type PIS-04-187 and right column (B),(D): sparger type PIS-05-120. Operating conditions: semi-batch mode. Symbols: experiments, inlet marked with star. Solid lines: simulation with measured inlet BSD. Dashed line: simulation with inlet BSD obtained by the sparger model.

As anticipated, the measured SMD and the local gas volume fraction demonstrate the expected

trends. Both values increase with increasing gas flux, irrespective of sparger type and axial position. The rise in gas volume fraction is attributable to the fact that a greater volume of gas must traverse the column (cf. [5]).

For the sparger PIS-05-120, an almost linear correlation was observed between the measured SMD and the axial position for each gas flux (see Fig. 4.1B). While rising in the column the number of coalescence events increases and thus the BSD shifts to larger diameters. In contrast, the profile of the measured SMD along the axial position for the sparger PIS-04-187 (see Fig. 4.1A) is not linear. The measured SMD first decreases and then it increases. Only the curves at higher gas fluxes ($j_d \geq 4.0$ cm/s) show a different form. A similar behavior was already observed in [6] for a semi-batch bubble column with an aqueous sodium chloride solution as liquid phase. The design of the column was similar to this work (diameter of the column $d_{BC} = 10$ cm, and diameter and number of the sparger orifices $d_h = 0.4$ mm, $N_h = 163$). At that time, we reached the conclusion that this behavior could be attributed to the invasiveness of the OMOP. In this study, measurements with the NP, which is significantly less invasive than the OMOP, confirmed that the axial profile of the SMD passes through a minimum. Furthermore, since this profile was not observed for high gas fluxes ($j_d > 4.0$ cm/s) and it did not occur when the sparger PIS-05-120 was employed (see Fig. 4.1B), it is assumed that the non-linear axial profile of the SMD is due to a complex interaction of bubble size-dependent breakage and, more importantly, coalescence (more on this later). A similar explanation applies to the fact that the SMD did not increase further with increasing axial position at the highest gas flux (cf. Fig. 4.1A). Again, this was also observed in our previous experiments with pure water as liquid phase [6]. We assumed that bubble size detection limitation of the OMOP could be the cause for that behavior. Also here, the new measurements with the NP, which were carried out in this work, do not confirm our previous assumption, but the experimental data is still too scarce to completely rule it out.

The local gas volume fraction for both spargers (see Fig. 4.1C and D) the for gas fluxes $j_d = (1 - 3)$ cm s⁻¹ is almost constant along the height of the column. For the two larger gas fluxes, the local gas volume fraction exhibits a slight decrease, which can be attributed to the fact that the large bubbles formed there have a significantly higher rise velocity, resulting in a reduction of the local gas volume fraction.

In general, the agreement between the model prediction and the experimental results is satisfactory. It is noteworthy that no calibration of the model parameters was conducted in this study; instead, all model parameters were directly adopted from our previous work [6]. Comparing the model prediction, of the case, in which the measured inlet BSD is used as boundary condition (solid line in Fig. 4.1A and B) for the two different spargers shows that the PIS-04-187 $MAPE_{\xi_{32},sim}^{M>1,j_d} = 13.4$ % is predicted significantly worse than the PIS-05-187 $MAPE_{\xi_{32},sim}^{M>1,j_d} = 7.7$ %. This finding can be attributed to the fact that the parameters calibrated by Breit *et al.* [6] and adopted by us in this work were obtained from bubble column experiments with similar a dispersed phase behavior to that of sparger PIS-05-187. In other words, no experimental results have been used for the model calibration thus far that show a comparable axial profile of the SMD to that observed with sparger PIS-04-187, in which the bubble diameter initially decreases after leaving the inlet and then increases. It is therefore unsurprising that the set of parameters estimated in our previous work does not yet provide an accurate representation

of the complex interplay between coalescence and breakage within the column as it is observed for that type of sparger. It is possible to make an additional adjustment to the second coalescence parameter, namely the coalescence efficiency parameter. This parameter was set by Breit *et al.* [6] to unity, as it was deemed to have no significant influence on the objective value, the error during calibration. When the value is unity, a coalescence efficiency of 100 % is obtained, regardless of bubble size. By modifying this parameter to obtain a bubble size dependent coalescence efficiency, a more complex dispersed phase behavior could be described. However, the aim of this work is not to recalibrate the parameters, but to investigate the prediction performance of our model, which has been calibrated with minimal experimental data. And this could be further demonstrated and extended in the case of PIS-05-187, so that higher gas fluxes could also be predicted well by the model, whereby the same limitation of the model at $j_d = 1 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ as with [6] can be observed here due to the flow regime change.

When the sparger model is used to predict the inlet BSD (boundary condition), a similar good agreement between experimental and model predictions with respect to the SMD of $MAPE_{\xi_{32}, \text{sim-SPM}}^{M>1, j_d} = 12.6 \%$ for the PIS-04-187 and $MAPE_{\xi_{32}, \text{sim-SPM}}^{M>1, j_d} = 8.5 \%$ for the PIS-05-120 can be observed, especially for lower gas fluxes (see dashed lines in Fig. 4.1). The fact that the model prediction for the case where the sparger model is used to describe the inlet BSD is slightly better than that where the measured inlet BSD is used can be attributed to the two higher gas fluxes (cf. Fig. 4.1A and B).

A comparison between the measured value and the model prediction demonstrates that the sparger model is capable of accurately describing the BSD at the inlet ($M = 1$) for both spargers: $MAPE_{\xi_{32}, \text{SPM}}^{M=1, j_d} = 2.1 \%$ for the PIS-04-187 and $MAPE_{\xi_{32}, \text{SPM}}^{M=1, j_d} = 4.7 \%$ for the PIS-05-120. Therefore, the prediction performance of the axial profiles of the SMD is not significantly affected in our case by the choice of boundary conditions, whether measured values or model predictions of the BSD are used (cf. Fig. 4.2 first column). Obviously, the sparger model adopted from Ribeiro *et al.* [15] and modified in this work is able to predict the inlet BSD, taking into account a limitation at higher gas fluxes.

Fig. 4.1C and D demonstrates that the model is capable of accurately predicting the axial profile of the local gas volume fraction, irrespective of the manner in which the inlet BSD is described: $MAPE_{\alpha_d, \text{sim}}^{M, j_d} = 8.2 \%$ and $MAPE_{\alpha_d, \text{sim-SPM}}^{M, j_d} = 7.6 \%$ for PIS-04-187 and $MAPE_{\alpha_d, \text{sim}}^{M, j_d} = 10.5 \%$ and $MAPE_{\alpha_d, \text{sim-SPM}}^{M, j_d} = 10.0 \%$ for the PIS-05-120. Only at higher gas fluxes ($j_d = 5 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$) the model exceeds the trend. It is important to note that no data pertaining to the gas holdup or the local gas volume were employed for the calibration of the model parameters. Therefore, it can be considered a pure model prediction. In particular, the gas volume fraction is a crucial parameter for engineers engaged in the design and optimization of bubble columns. It influences a number of key factors, including the maximum possible liquid holdup in the column, interfacial heat and mass transfer, and the conversion of reactants. The favorable outcome serves to reinforce the efficacy of the proposed model approach.

Fig. 4.2 illustrates a comparison between the measured and predicted BSD for three distinct axial positions within the column, as well as for varying gas fluxes associated with the PIS-05-120 sparger. The same figure for the PIS-04-187 is presented in the Supplementary Information Fig. S.3.

As previously observed in our research [6], the distributions become broader with increasing gas flux and axial position, and are shifted towards larger bubble diameters. This can be attributed to an increase in coalescence events analogous to the moments. Overall, the MPB approach have a prediction performance of $\overline{\chi^2_{sim}}^{M>1,j_d} = 0.05/\text{mm}$ and $\overline{\chi^2_{sim-SPM}}^{M>1,j_d} = 0.09/\text{mm}$ for the PIS-04-187 and $\overline{\chi^2_{sim}}^{M>1,j_d} = 0.07/\text{mm}$ and $\overline{\chi^2_{sim-SPM}}^{M>1,j_d} = 0.15/\text{mm}$ for the PIS-05-120 sparger.

Figure 4.2.: Normalized number density distribution \hat{f}_d^n as a function of bubble diameter ξ for different gas fluxes j_d (color, along rows) and axial positions z (along columns) for the PIS-05-120 sparger in semi-batch mode. Symbols: experiments, inlet marked with star. Solid lines: simulation with measured inlet BSD. Dashed line: simulation with inlet BSD obtained by the sparger model.

The prediction performance of the sparger model with respect to the inlet BSD are $\overline{\chi^2}_{\text{sim-SPM}}^{M=1,j_d} = 0.05/\text{mm}$ for the PIS-04-187 and $\overline{\chi^2}_{\text{sim-SPM}}^{M=1,j_d} = 0.07/\text{mm}$ for the PIS-05-120 results. Both the χ^2 -values as well as the BSDs plotted in Fig. 4.2 reveals that the prediction performance is enhanced when the measured inlet BSD is utilized as the boundary condition, as opposed to the inlet BSD predicted by the sparger model. As previously stated, when only the SMD and gas volume fraction (moments) are considered, the origin of the inlet BSD is inconsequential. This illustrates that an evaluation of the model's prediction performance based solely on the moments may lead to wrong conclusions.

Moreover, it can be observed that the model with the parameters of Breit *et al.* [6] exhibits a tendency to underestimate coalescence and overestimate breakage, as evidenced by a significant discrepancy between the measured BSD and those predicted by the model. Furthermore, the inlet BSD, as predicted by the sparger model, also deteriorates with increasing gas flux and remains overly peaked (see Fig. 4.2A-M). The error persists in the BSDs of axial positions situated at greater distances from the inlet. It is noteworthy that the model predicts a bimodal distribution at the highest flux and position (see Fig. 4.2O), despite the specification of a mono-modal log-normal inlet BSD which is attributed to the complex interplay between breakage and coalescence. It is intensified by the higher gas flux and thus energy dissipation.

It should be mentioned that a better prediction of the distributions is possible with the help of the sparger model, in which, for example, not the moments (ξ_{32}, σ^2) but the χ^2 -distance of the BSDs is added to the objective function for the parameter estimation in the fourth step of the modified sparger model (see Supplementary Information S.2). However, this can lead to a poor prediction of the moments. In essence, neither the SMD nor the BSD is of direct interest to the engineer, but rather, the influence of these values on the apparatus' overall performance is of greater consequence., e.g. on conversion and yield. So far it is not clear which of the properties of the dispersed flow must be predicted most accurately in order to describe the overall performance of the apparatus best. This question will be addressed in future work in which reaction and / or separation processes in dispersed gas-liquid systems will be studied.

Nevertheless, it can be concluded that the parameters of Breit *et al.* [6] can be directly applied for other spargers and higher gas fluxes as they have been used in the calibration experiments and still they enable a prediction of the BSDs, the SMD and the local gas volume fraction with a deviation (compared to the experimental data) of less than 10 %. Furthermore, the developed modified sparger model shows good inter- and extrapolation capabilities and provides only a slightly poorer prediction performance than with measured inlet BSD. Moreover, the parameters of Breit *et al.* [6] appear to be independent of the measurement technique (OMOP versus NP) employed to quantify the BSD required for parameter calibration and specification of the inlet BSD. The results thus confirm the hypothesis that the choice of measurement technique has no influence on the model parameters and prediction performance (cf. Section 1). So no or just little information about the inlet BSD is lumped in to the model parameters while parameter calibration. Furthermore, it can be stated that it is most important for a good parameter calibration to capture the trends how the BSD develops along the axial position in the column and not to measure the absolute values of the BSD. However, the kernels used here and many other kernels depend on the order of magnitude of the bubble size examined, so that the parameters

can only be applied to similar size ranges.

4.2. Continuous Mode – Gas and Liquid Flux Study

Fig. 4.3 depicts the SMD ξ_{32} and the local gas volume fraction α_d as a function of the axial position in the bubble column for the continuous mode for different gas fluxes j_d now for different liquid fluxes j_c along the columns of the figure.

Figure 4.3.: Top row A-C: Sauter mean diameter ξ_{32} and bottom row D-F: local gas volume fraction as function of the axial position z for different gas fluxes j_d (color) and liquid fluxes j_c (columns). Operating conditions: continuous mode. Symbols: experiments, inlet marked with star. Solid lines: simulation with measured inlet BSD. Dashed line: simulation with inlet BSD obtained by the sparger model.

First, the experimental results shown in Fig. 4.3 are discussed. As expected, the SMD (see Fig. 4.3A-C) increases with the gas flux and axial position analogous. The strongly curved profiles observed for the semi-batch mode, in which the SMD even decreased first, are not found in the experiments of the continuous mode. The slope of the profiles becomes greater with increasing liquid flux, which is attributed to the higher energy dissipation caused by the liquid feed. It is postulated that the nearly linear profile observed in the continuous mode is attributable to the well-defined co-current flow of both the gas and liquid phases. In contrast, in the semi-batch mode, which lacks forced convection of the liquid phase, circulation zones with strong backmixing are evident in the column. Additionally, slightly larger SMD are observed in the continuous mode (for the same gas flux and axial position) in comparison to the semi-batch

mode. This finding is attributed to the increased energy dissipation by the liquid flow. The axial profiles of the local gas volume fraction (see Fig. 4.3D-F) show a similar behavior in the continuous mode as in the semi-batch mode. The local gas volume fraction remains relatively constant along the axial position, which is consistent with the findings observed in the semi-batch mode for the majority of gas fluxes. However, no decrease was detected for the highest gas flux, in contrast to the results obtained in the semi-batch mode (cf. Fig. 4.1D).

A comparison of the model predictions with the experimental data demonstrates that the model is capable of accurately predicting the axial profiles of the SMD and the local gas volume fraction for all liquid fluxes, provided that the gas fluxes are low ($j_d \leq 2.0 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$). The errors are: $MAPE_{\xi_{32}, \text{sim}}^{M>1, \{j_d\} \leq 2, j_c} = 2.9 \%$ and $MAPE_{\xi_{32}, \text{sim-SPM}}^{M>1, \{j_d\} \leq 2, j_c} = 5.3 \%$. The high gas fluxes ($j_d \geq 3.0 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$) can only be predicted for the lowest liquid flux (cf. Fig. 4.3A). It is hypothesized that this behavior is derived from the model employed to describe the turbulent energy dissipation rate. In accordance with the model proposed by Baird *et al.* [25], the turbulent energy dissipation rate is assumed to be constant within the reactor, dependent solely on the gas flux and liquid flux. As the turbulent energy dissipation rate affects both the breakage and coalescence kernels, it exerts a considerable influence on the BSD within the column. A sensitivity analysis (not shown here) indicates that the prediction performance of the model can be enhanced when the turbulent energy dissipation rate is increased. This observation implies that the basic model proposed by Baird *et al.* [25] may underestimate the turbulent energy dissipation rate for higher gas and liquid fluxes. In accordance with the fundamental principles of physics, turbulence is a transient three-dimensional phenomenon. Consequently, it is a gross oversimplification to reduce this phenomenon to a constant value that is applicable throughout the entire column. In future work, the development of turbulent models that provide a more accurate representation of the local turbulent energy dissipation rate while maintaining consistency with the steady-state and one-dimensional MPB approach will be addressed.

A comparison of the two approaches utilized to define the inlet BSD (experimental data or prediction by the sparger model) demonstrates that even for a spider sparger and continuous mode, the sparger model accurately predicts the SMD. The resulting error is: $MAPE_{\xi_{32}, \text{SPM}}^{M=1, j_d, j_c} = 6.3 \%$. It should be noted that only for the smallest liquid flux $j_c = 1 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ the sparger model parameters were adjusted as described in Supplementary Information S.2. Therefore, the simulation results shown in Fig. 4.3B-F are pure model predictions without any prior knowledge about the experiments to be reproduced. Overall, this results in a $MAPE_{\xi_{32}, \text{sim}}^{M>1, j_d, j_c} = 8.7 \%$ and $MAPE_{\xi_{32}, \text{sim-SPM}}^{M>1, j_d, j_c} = 10.1 \%$ for the model with specification of the measured inlet BSD and for the model with an inlet BSD from the sparger model. The profiles of the gas volume fraction are accurately predicted by the model comparable to the results found for the semi-batch mode (see Fig. 4.3D-F), $MAPE_{\alpha_d, \text{sim}}^{M, j_d, j_c} = 9.8 \%$ and $MAPE_{\alpha_d, \text{sim-SPM}}^{M, j_d, j_c} = 10.2 \%$.

Fig 4.4 depicts the BSD measured in the continuous mode for a liquid flux of $j_c = 2 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ at different axial positions and for different gas fluxes (the remaining j_c are given in the Supplementary Information Fig. S.4 and Fig. S.5). It is evident that the measured distributions exhibit a narrower range for all axial positions and gas fluxes. The degree of prediction performance is comparable to that observed in the semi-batch mode: $\overline{\chi^2}_{\text{sim}}^{M>1, j_d, j_c} = 0.04/\text{mm}$ and $\overline{\chi^2}_{\text{sim-SPM}}^{M>1, j_d, j_c} = 0.10/\text{mm}$. The prediction performance of sparger model for the inlet BSD is also

comparable to that found for the semi-batch mode: $\overline{\chi^2}_{\text{SPM}}^{M=1, j_d, j_c} = 0.05/\text{mm}$. The good agreement between predicted inlet BSD and measured BSD is the reason why the differences between the model predictions of the axial profiles of the BSD, SMD and gas volume fraction obtained from the two different inlet BSD (sparger model and measured) are not significant.

Despite the certain deviations in the model predictions found for higher gas fluxes, it must be emphasized that the model parameters of Breit *et al.* [6] were calibrated for the semi-batch mode and could be applied here without adjustment to the continuous mode. This means that the 1D-MPB reflects the underlying physical principles, so that this information was not or only to a small extent lumped into the parameters.

Figure 4.4.: Normalized number density distribution \hat{f}_d^n as a function of bubble diameter ξ for different gas fluxes j_d (color, along rows) and axial positions z (along columns) for the liquid flux $j_c = 2 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. Symbols: experiments, inlet marked with star. Solid lines: simulation with measured inlet BSD. Dashed line: simulation with inlet BSD obtained by the sparger model.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

In this study, we extended the assessment of the prediction performance of a one-dimensional multifluid population balance model (1D-MPB) for bubble columns by evaluating its prediction performance in both semi-batch and continuous co-current operation. The model parameters were adopted from previous work and were not recalibrated in this work. During the experiments, we used a variety of sparger types and varied the gas and liquid fluxes. In this study, we employed a fiber optic needle probe for data acquisition, as this method is less invasive than the multimode online optical probe (OMOP) used in previous investigations [5, 6]. This allowed the acquisition of bubble size distribution (BSD) and local gas volume fraction data at elevated gas fluxes.

The main results of our study highlight that the model showed good prediction performance for different spargers, especially at lower gas fluxes during semi-batch operation. The model predictions of Sauter mean diameter (SMD), local gas volume fraction and BSDs were in good agreement with the experimental data, especially when the inlet bubble size distribution (BSD) was measured. We propose a modified sparger model based on the model of Ribeiro *et al.* [15]. This modified sparger model was calibrated with only two measured inlet BSDs. The use of this modified sparger model to predict the inlet BSD for different sparger types (plate and spider), gas and liquid fluxes showed potential, although limitations were observed at higher gas fluxes.

Our results also show that the model fit parameters are independent of the measurement method used to determine the reference BSD. So that model parameters calibrated with measured BSD using the OMOP could be used to predict BSD measured with needle probes. This underlines that the parameter calibration, or estimation method, used together with the MPB generalizes to the changes and not to the magnitude of the BSDs. The magnitude of the BSD (e.g. the mean) predicted by the model is determined exclusively by the inlet BSD and is either not or only to a minimal extent lumped into the model parameters.

In continuous co-current operation, the model's prediction performance was also effective, with good agreement between predicted and experimental SMD, local gas volume fractions and BSDs over a range of gas and liquid fluxes. Model parameters were not recalibrated, so parameters obtained in a semi-batch column were applied to the continuous mode. The fact that this was possible supports the physical principles described by the MPB and demonstrates the great potential of this model approach for scaling up dispersed multiphase processes from laboratory experiments.

Despite these achievements presented in our two studies [5, 6], this study identified several limitations in the current model approach. The model's reliance on calibrated parameters from semi-batch mode experiments may not fully capture the dynamics in the co-current mode. In addition, the underestimation of turbulent energy dissipation rates at higher fluxes suggests

the need for more sophisticated modeling approaches that account for spatial variations in this value. Further refinement of the sparger model toward a predictive model without the need for experimental data for calibration is also necessary to more accurately predict inlet BSDs over a broader range of operating conditions.

By addressing these areas, the 1D-MPB approach can be further optimized to provide a powerful tool for the design and optimization of bubble columns in various industrial applications. Further development and validation of this model approach will contribute significantly to the understanding and control of multiphase flow processes, facilitating optimization, design and scale-up from laboratory to production scale reactors.

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Nomenclature

Latin Letters

A	Cross-sectional area	m^2
c	Sparger parameter	-
C_1, \dots, C_4	Parameters of the breakage and coalescence kernel	$(-, m^{-2}, -, -)$
d	Diameter, pipe diameter	m
d_{BC}	Inner diameter of the bubble column	m
d_h	Orifice diameter	m
f_d^m	Mass based density function	$kg\ m^{-4}$
f_d^n	Number based density function	m^{-4}
f	Distribution function	
g	Gravitational acceleration constant	$m\ s^{-2}$
h	Height	m
h_c	Ungasified liquid height	m
j_k	Volume flux of the k -phase	$m\ s^{-1}, cm\ s^{-1}$
$MAPE$	Mean absolute percentage error	%
n	Normalizing index	-
N	Number incorporated moments and experiments	-
N_h	Number of orifices in a sparger	-
N_ξ	Number of discretization points in property space	-
N_z	Number of discretization points in physical space	-
p^0	Ambient pressure	Pa
p_1	Slope parameter of the sparger function	$s\ cm^{-1}$
p_2	y-intercept of the sparger function	-
T^0	Ambient temperature	K
$V_d(\xi)$	Volume of bubble with size ξ	m^3
z	Axial position coordinate along the main flow direction	m

Greek Letters

α_d	Volume fraction of the gas phase	-
ϵ	Termination criterion of the non-linear solver	-
ϵ	Turbulent energy dissipation rate	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-3}$
μ_k	Viscosity of the k -phase	Pas
μ_{ab}	ab moment ratio of a distribution function	$\text{m}^{(a-b)}$
ξ	Bubble size	m
ξ_0	Variable around which the moment is formed	
ξ_{10}	Arithmetic mean	m
ξ_{30}	Volume-equivalent mean diameter	m
$\xi_{30,h}$	Volume-equivalent mean diameter from at a sparger orifice	m
ξ_{32}	Sauter mean diameter	m
ρ_k	Mass density of the k -phase	kg m^{-3}
σ	Surface tension between of the continuous and dispersed phase	J m^{-2}
σ	Standard deviation of a distribution	m
σ^2	Variance of a distribution	m
χ	Second parameter of a log-normal distribution function	-
χ^2	Chi-Square distance	m^{-1}
ω	First parameter of a log-normal distribution function, sparger function	-

Subscripts

ab	Order of the μ_{ab} moment ratio
c	Continuous liquid phase
conti	Quantity with reference to co-current mode
d	Dispersed gas phase
exp	Quantity resulting from a experiment
h	Quantity with reference to a sparger orifice
i	Index of incorporated moments and/or experiments
inlet	Quantity at the inlet
j	Index of the bubble size class
k	Phase index
max	Upper bound
min	Lower bound
semi-batch	Quantity with reference to semi-batch mode

Superscripts

^	Normalized quantity
-	Averaged quantity
0	Reference state
ini	Initial guess value
m	Mass based quantity
n	Number based quantity

Abbreviations

1D	One-dimensional in physical space
2D	Two-dimensional in physical space
BC	Bubble column
BSD	Bubble size distributions
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
CLD	Chord length distribution
FVMG	Finite volume method with Gauss quadrature
GLL	Gauss-Legendre-Lobatto
KTAWSR	Kinetic theory with size resolution
M1, M2, M3	Measuring position
MPB	Multifluid population balance model
NP	Needle probe
OMOP	Optical multimode online probe
OPTOEM	Optoelectronic module
PBE	Population balance equation
PIS	Plate sparger
SMD	Sauter mean diameter
SpS	Spider sparger

Note if a variable has no unit this is indicated by -, if no specification is made the unit of the variable can change.

S. Supplementary Information

S.1. Additional Equations

S.1.1. Transformation of Mass to Number Based Density Function

In order to calculate the number weighted moments, the mass density function f_d^m is transformed into a number density function f_d^n using the Eq. (S.1).

$$f_d^n(\xi, z) = \frac{f_d^m(\xi, z)}{V_d(\xi)\rho_d(z)} \quad (\text{S.1})$$

(S.2)

Where $V_d(\xi)$ is the volume of a spherical bubble with size ξ and $\rho_d(z)$ is the mass density of the dispersed phase.

S.1.2. Moments

The ab -th moment ratio μ_{ab} of a distribution function $f(\xi - \xi_0)$ of a variable ξ about ξ_0 is defined as:

$$\mu_{ab} = \left(\frac{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \xi^a f(\xi - \xi_0) d\xi}{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \xi^b f(\xi - \xi_0) d\xi} \right)^{n/(a-b)} \quad (\text{S.3})$$

where ab are the order of the moment ratio and n is the normalizing index with $n = 1$ - normalized and $n = 0$ non-normalized. In order to calculate some characteristic quantities of a distribution derived from the moment ratio Tab. S.1 is used.

Table S.1.: Characteristic quantities of a distribution derived from the moment ratio.

a	b	n	ξ	f	ξ_0	Name	Symbol
1	0	1	ξ	f_d^n	0	Arithmetic mean	ξ_{10}
2	0	1	ξ	f_d^n	ξ_{10}	Standard deviation	
2	0	0	ξ	f_d^n	ξ_{10}	Variance	σ^2
3	0	0	$(\xi - \xi_{10})/\sigma$	f_d^n	0	Skewness	
4	0	0	$(\xi - \xi_{10})/\sigma$	f_d^n	0	Kurtosis	
3	2	1	ξ	f_d^n	0	Sauter mean diameter	ξ_{32}
2	0	1	ξ	f_d^n	0	Surface-equivalent mean diameter	
3	0	1	ξ	f_d^n	0	Volume-equivalent mean diameter	ξ_{30}

S.1.3. Normalization

In order to compare the experimental and predicted BSD, the simulated mass based density function $f_d^m(\xi, z)$ must be converted to a number based density function $f_d^n(\xi, z)$ using Eq. (S.1) and then normalized using Eq. (S.4).

$$\hat{f}_d^n(\xi, z) = \frac{f_d^n(\xi, z)}{\int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} f_d^n(\xi, z) d\xi} \quad (\text{S.4})$$

Here \hat{f}_d^n is the normalized number based density function.

S.1.4. Local Gas Volume Fraction

The local gas volume fraction α_d follows directly from the mass density function using the Eq. (S.5).

$$\alpha_d(z) = \frac{\int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} f_d^m(\xi, z) d\xi}{\rho_d(z)} \quad (\text{S.5})$$

Here ξ_{\min}, ξ_{\max} are the minimal resp. the maximal bubble size considered in the calculations.

S.2. Sparger Model

In the following, a five-step modification of the sparger model according to Ribeiro *et al.* [15], which consists only of steps (1,2,5), is presented in order to determine the inlet BSD $\hat{f}_{d,\text{inlet}}^n$.

1. In the first step, the volume mean diameter $\xi_{30,h}$ is calculated using the model according to Geary *et al.* [23] based on property data (liquid, gas mass density and viscosity, surface tension) and the sparger geometry consisting of the orifice diameter d_h and the number of orifices N_h . The number of orifices is used to calculate the volume flow rate through the single orifice for which the model according to Geary *et al.* [23] was developed.
2. In the second step, the two parameters (χ, ω) of a log-normal distribution Eq. (S.6) are fitted to measured inlet BSD for different gas fluxes in our case $j_d = (2, 4) \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ to be in line with the available gas fluxes of the breakage and coalescence parameter calibration (cf. Breit *et al.* [6]). For this purpose, the minimization problem Eq. (S.7) is solved.

$$\hat{f}_{d,\text{inlet}}^n(\xi, \chi, \omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\xi\chi} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\ln(\xi) - \chi}{\sqrt{2}\omega}\right)^2\right) \quad (\text{S.6})$$

$$\min_{\chi, \omega} \left\| \sum_{i,j} \hat{f}_{d,\text{inlet}}^n(\xi_j, \chi_i, \omega_i) - \hat{f}_{d,\text{inlet},\text{exp}}^n(\xi_j, j_{d,i}) \right\|_2^2 \quad (\text{S.7})$$

3. In the third step, the resulting value pairs of $j_{d,i}, \omega_i$ of the previous step are fitted via linear regression to the gas flux dependent sparger function Eq. (S.8).

$$\omega(j_d) = p_1 j_d + p_2 \quad (\text{S.8})$$

4. In the fourth step, the parameter c is determined by solving the minimization problem Eq. (S.9).

$$\min_{\chi, c} \left\| \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} \xi^3 \hat{f}_{d, \text{inlet}}^n(\xi, \chi_i, \omega) d\xi - c \xi_{30, h, i} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{|\xi_{32, i, \text{exp}} - \xi_{32, i}|}{\xi_{32, i, \text{exp}}} + \frac{|\sigma_{i, \text{exp}} - \sigma_i|}{\sigma_{i, \text{exp}}} \right) \right\|_2^2 \quad (\text{S.9})$$

In addition to the ξ_{30} of the distribution $\hat{f}_{d, \text{inlet}}^n(\xi, \chi_i, \omega)$, further moments namely the SMD ξ_{32} and the standard deviation σ in comparison to experiments using the *MAPE* were included in the minimization, so that further moments of the distribution are also optimized. It was found that the best results could be achieved when $\omega(j_d = 4 \text{ cm}^{-1})$ was kept constant.

5. In the fifth and final step, the minimization problem Eq. (S.10) is solved with the now determined sparger parameter c and sparger function $\omega(j_d)$ in order to obtain the final χ of the log-normal distribution.

$$\min_{\chi} \left\| \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} \xi^3 \hat{f}_{d, \text{inlet}}^n(\xi, \chi_i, \omega(j_d)) d\xi - c \xi_{30, h, i} \right\|_2^2 \quad (\text{S.10})$$

This polishing step was additionally carried out because due to the now constant c , better χ can be found which has led to an overall better prediction performance.

Note that despite the multiple minimizations, only the measured distributions for the gas fluxes $j_d = (2, 4) \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ are used.

After the procedure has been run once, an inlet BSD can be obtained at any gas flux using the parameter c , the sparger function $\omega(j_d)$ and step 1 and 5 of the procedure. However, the limitation of the model according to Geary *et al.* [23] must be considered, which only applies up to $Re = 500$, which is still fulfilled for $j_d = 4 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ and is slightly exceeded for $j_d = 5 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, it was nevertheless used.

The sparger model was implemented in MATLAB[®] in Version R2023a (9.14.0.2286388) from the publisher The MathWorks Inc. (Natick, Massachusetts, USA) using the functions: `fsolve` (step 1), `lsqcurvefit` (step 2), `polyfit` (step 3) and `lsqnonlin` (step 4,5).

The result of the sparger model using the property data, Tab. S.3 and the sparger geometry, Tab. S.7 is summarized in Tab. S.5 and Tab. S.6.

S.3. Applied Parameters in the Simulations

Tab. S.2 summarizes the initial conditions of the non-linear solver presented in Breit *et al.* [5], the boundary conditions and further model parameters. Tab. S.3 presents the property data of pure water and air together with solver related parameters and the calibrated parameter of the breakage and coalescence parameter of the model according to Coualaloglou *et al.* [26] calibrated from Breit *et al.* [6]. Tab. S.5 shows the parameters of the sparger function Eq. (S.8) and sparger parameter c resulting from the sparger model, presented in Section S.2. The corresponding parameters of the log-normal distribution Eq. (S.6) are depicted in Tab. S.5. The measured inlet BSD as a boundary condition for f_d^m are summarized in the Supplementary Material.

Table S.2.: Initial and boundary conditions and model parameters used in the simulations.

Parameter	Unit	Value
d_{BC}	m	0.10635
$h_{c,semi-batch}$	m	1.8
$h_{c,conti}$	m	result of calc.
$h_{BC,semi-batch}$	m	result of calc.
$h_{BC,conti}$	m	2.535
$j_{c,semi-batch}$	m s^{-1}	1×10^{-6}
$j_{c,conti}$	cm s^{-1}	1 - 3
j_d	cm s^{-1}	1 - 5
p^0	Pa	101500
$\alpha_d^{\text{ini}}(z)$	-	0.1
h_{BC}^{ini}	-	2.4
$p^{\text{ini}}(z_{\text{min}})$	Pa	120884
g	m s^{-2}	9.81

Table S.3.: Left: Property data pure of water and of air. Right: solver related parameter applied in the simulations.

<i>Property data</i>			<i>Solver related parameter</i>		
Parameter	Unit	Value	Parameter	Unit	Value
μ_c	Pas	9.7754×10^{-4}	ξ_{min}	m	5×10^{-5}
μ_d	Pas	18×10^{-6}	ξ_{max}	m	20×10^{-3}
σ	J m^{-2}	0.072	$z_{\text{min},\text{semi-batch}}, z_{\text{min},\text{conti}}$	m	0.195, 0.162
ρ_d^0	kg m^{-3}	1.188	$\{\epsilon\}$	-	1×10^{-6}
ρ_c	kg m^{-3}	998	N_ξ	-	89
T^0	K	293	N_z	-	14

Table S.4.: Parameters of the used breakage and coalescence kernel according to Coulaloglou *et al.* [26] adapted from Chapter ??.

<i>Breakage and coalescence</i>		
Parameter	Unit	Value
C_1	-	0.0111
C_2	m^{-2}	1
C_3	-	0.2130
C_4	-	4.4704

Table S.5.: Parameters of the sparger function Eq. (S.8) and the sparger parameter c resulting from the sparger model presented in Section S.2.

Sparger	$p_1/\text{s cm}^{-1}$	$p_2/-$	$c/-$
PlS-04-187	0.0354	0.3958	0.7003
PlS-05-120	0.0196	0.4231	0.5533
SpS-04-56	0.0324	0.3788	0.5143

Table S.6.: Parameters of the log-normal distribution Eq. (S.6) resulting from the sparger model (cf. Section S.2).

$j_d / \text{cm s}^{-1}$	Log-normal parameter χ, ω		
	PIS-04-187	PIS-05-120	SpS-04-56
1	0.4500, 0.4112	0.4111, 0.4428	0.4499, 0.4112
2	0.5942, 0.4667	0.5013, 0.4624	0.5453, 0.4436
3	0.6140, 0.5021	0.5553, 0.4820	0.5784, 0.4760
4	0.6141, 0.5375	0.5888, 0.5016	0.5797, 0.5084
5	0.6000, 0.5729	0.6087, 0.5212	-

The name of a sparger is made up of three parts: firstly the type plate sparger (PIS) or spider sparger (SpS), secondly the single orifice diameter in tenths of a millimeter and thirdly the number of orifices.

S.4. Detail about the Experimental Setup

Tab. S.7 provides the abbreviations of the spargers and details of their design. Tab. S.8 summarizes the set parameters of the OPTOEM and the associated software M2 Analyzer for Bubbles v2.25 from the publisher A2 Photonic Sensors (Grenoble, France). The geometric dimensions of the needle probes used in this work are depicted in Fig. S.1. The exact axial measuring position of the needle probes is shown in Tab. S.9.

Table S.7.: Geometric dimensions used for the plate sparger (PIS) and the spider sparger (SpS). Here d_h is the single orifice diameter, the number of orifices N_h and the ratio of the total orifice area to the cross-sectional area of the bubble column A_h/A_{BC} .

Disperser	d_h / mm	$N_h / -$	$A_h/A_{BC} / -$
PIS-04-187	0.4	187	0.0106
PIS-05-120	0.5	120	0.0106
SpS-04-56	0.4	56	0.00317

Table S.8.: Parameter settings of the optoelectronic module and the software.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Refractive index of the continuous phase	1.33	-
Refractive index of the dispersed phase	1.00	-
Sampling frequency during gas fraction measurement	801.28	kHz
Pretrigger	500	μs
Velocity filter	-	-
Size filter	-	-
Duration filter	-	-
FFT amplitude filter	-	-
Deviation factor of the liquid threshold (start value autosest parameters)	10	-
Minimum number of strips (start value autosest parameters)	30	-
Spectral-temporal homogeneity (start value autosest parameters)	90	%
Liquid threshold (start value autosest parameters)	0	mV
Bandpass low frequency (start value autosest parameters)	100	kHz
Bandpass high frequency (start value autosest parameters)	100	kHz
Trigger level of the gas fraction measurement	0.25	V
Laser Intensity	[1,4]	V

Figure S.1.: Design and dimensions of the needle probe used.

Table S.9.: Heights of the measuring positions, measured from the sparger.

Measuring position	Semi-batch	Continuous	Unit
M1	0.195	0.162	m
M2	0.967	0.934	m
M3	1.715	1.682	m

S.5. Additional Figures

This section summarizes all additional figures.

Figure S.2.: Normalized number density distribution \hat{f}_d^n as a function of bubble diameter ξ measured with the OMOP (solid line with point marker) and with the NP (solid line with triangle marker) at gas flux j_d above the PIS-04-187 sparger. Substance System: water-air.

Figure S.3.: Normalized number density distribution \hat{f}_d^n as a function of bubble diameter ξ for different gas fluxes j_d (color, along rows) and axial positions z (along columns) for the PIS-04-187 sparger. Symbols: experiments, inlet marked with star. Solid lines: simulation with measured inlet BSD. Dashed line: simulation with inlet BSD obtained by the sparger model.

Figure S.4.: Normalized number density distribution \hat{f}_d^n as a function of bubble diameter ξ for different gas fluxes j_d (color, along rows) and axial positions z (along columns) for the liquid flux $j_c = 1 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. Symbols: experiments, inlet marked with star. Solid lines: simulation with measured inlet BSD. Dashed line: simulation with inlet BSD obtained by the sparger model.

Figure S.5.: Normalized number density distribution \hat{f}_d^n as a function of bubble diameter ξ for different gas fluxes j_d (color, along rows) and axial positions z (along columns) for the liquid flux $j_c = 3 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. Symbols: experiments, inlet marked with star. Solid lines: simulation with measured inlet BSD. Dashed line: simulation with inlet BSD obtained by the sparger model.